

3-Phenylthiazolid-2, 4-dione and some of its Derivatives

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3-Phenylthiazolid-2,4-dione was obtained by the method of Markley and Reid (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 2137) (cf. Liebermann and Voltzkow, *Ber.*, 1880, **13**, 276; Wheeler and Barnes, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, **24**, 60, etc.).

Decomposition of this thiazolidione with caustic potash and dry distillation with sodalime, its reactions with benzaldehyde, and preparation of its acetoxymercuri derivative by an improved procedure (cf. Rout, this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 690; Rout and Pujari, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 12) have been studied. Oxidation of the thiazolidione with potassium permanganate in acetic acid furnished the corresponding sulphone.

3-Phenylthiazolid-2,4-dione.—*S*-Diphenylthiourea (5 g.) and monochloroacetic acid (4 g.) were refluxed on a water bath in glacial acetic acid for about 2 hours. HCl (conc., 1.5 c.c.) was then added and refluxing continued for two and half hours more. The clear liquid was poured into water when a precipitate was obtained. It was washed with cold water to free it from excess acids, filtered, dried, and recrystallised from ethanol in the form of bushy rosettes of long, thin, faint yellow needles, yield 6g., m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 7.34. $C_9H_7O_2NS$ requires N, 7.25%).

Hydrolysis of 3-Phenyl-2-phenyliminothiazolid-4-one to 3-Phenylthiazolid-2,4-dione.—A mixture of 3-phenyl-2-phenyliminothiazolid-4-one (1.5 g.), ethanol (12 c.c.), and HCl (conc., 2 c.c.) was refluxed for 3½ hours. Ethanol was then distilled and water added; the precipitate which appeared was washed with cold water to remove acid and it was recrystallised from ethanol, yield 0.8 g., m.p. 148°. (Found: N, 7.29. $C_9H_7O_2NS$ requires N, 7.25%).

Decomposition with Potassium Hydroxide.—3-Phenylthiazolid-2,4-dione (1 g.) was heated with 40% KOH (30 c.c.) for 2½ hours. From the reaction mixture a liquid was isolated which was characterised as aniline by preparing its acetyl and azo- β -naphthol derivatives.

Dry Distillation with Sodalime.—The thiazolid-2, 4-dione (2 g.) was mixed with twice its weight of sodalime and subjected to dry distillation. The liquid thus obtained was identified to be aniline as in the above experiment.

5-Benzylidene-3-phenylthiazolid-2,4-dione.—A mixture of 3-phenylthiazolid-2,4-dione (1 g.), glacial acetic acid (10 c.c.), benzaldehyde (2 c.c.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (1.5 g.) was heated on an asbestos wire-gauze for 2 hrs. Water was added in excess and the mixture allowed to stand overnight. The precipitate was collected and recrystallised from acetic acid in light yellow crystals; yield 1.2g., m.p. 206°. (Found: N, 4.96; S, 11.42. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2NS$ requires N, 4.98; S, 11.37%).

3-Acetoxymercuriphenylthiazolid-2, 4-dione.—To 3-phenylthiazolid-2, 4-dione (1 g.), dissolved in ethanol-acetic acid, was added mercuric acetate (1.66 g.), dissolved in water acidified with acetic acid. The mixture was stirred vigorously and kept overnight. The precipitate was collected and washed repeatedly with hot water and dilute acetic acid. Finally it was washed several times with hot ethanol. The compound was isolated as a very light yellow powder, yield 1.22 g. (53% of theory), m.p. 246-48°. (Found: Hg, 44.49. $C_{11}H_9O_4NSHg$ requires Hg, 44.42%). The yield improved to 58% by directly refluxing for 15 minutes.

3-Phenylthiazolid-2, 4-dione-sulphone.—3-Phenylthiazolid-2,4-dione (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (20 c. c.) and treated slowly with potassium permanganate (1 g.) in water (25 c.c.) at 0°. After the reaction, excess of potassium permanganate was removed by treatment with sulphurous acid and the solution chilled with ice, when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with ice-water, dried, and crystallised from ethanol in a light greyish powder; yield 0.98 g. (85% of theory), m.p. 250°. (Found: N, 6.19. $C_9H_7O_4NS$ requires N, 6.22%).

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